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This volume of contains the extended abstracts or full papers accepted for presentation in the *IRF2020 - 7th International Conference on Integrity-Reliability-Failure* planned to be held in Funchal/Portugal, 6-10 Sep 2020. The document is published online for free access, from where an e-book version of the conference Proceedings can also be downloaded.

IRF2020 is the seventh international gathering of a prestigious series of Integrity-Reliability-Failure conferences coordinated by the International Scientific Committee of Mechanics and Materials in Design. This series of conferences are wholly devoted to advances in mechanics, materials, structural integrity and design.

The organisation of IRF2020 was jointly sponsored by the University of Porto, the University of Toronto and the Portuguese Society of Experimental Mechanics. The conference attracted over 250 contributions, with 216 accepted submissions involving 593 authors from 36 different countries around the world.

The conference themes, which address novel and advanced topics on Integrity, Reliability and Failure, focused on Theory, Experiments and Applications in Engineering, including Computational Mechanics, Experimental Mechanics, Fracture and Fatigue, Composite and Advanced Materials, Tribology and Surface Engineering, Mechanical Design and Prototyping, Biomechanical Applications, Civil and Structural Engineering Applications, Energy and Thermo-Fluid Systems, and Industrial Engineering and Management, among other topics.

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PROCEEDINGS IRF2020

7th International Conference Integrity - Reliability - Failure
Funchal/Portugal, 6-10 September 2020

Editors
J.F. Silva Gomes
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PECULIARITY OF ABSORBING INELASTIC PROPERTIES OF NANOCOMPOSITES MULTIWALLED CARBON NANOTUBES AND POLYETHYLENE, POLYVINYL CHLORIDE, EXPANDED POLYSTYRENE

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ABSTRACT

The interaction between structure defects and dislocations influences on the relaxation processes. A non-destructive method for the technological control of the structure defects by measuring the elastic module E and internal friction Q^{-1} was developed. The study of influence of nanostructure changing on attenuation of elastic vibrations in SiO_2 , TiO_2 allows to estimate the degree of defect structure.

Keywords: technological control, defects, strains fields, elastic vibrations, attenuation.

INTRODUCTION

Influence of deformation ε on a phonon spectrum is described by means of Gryunayzen constant γ . The changing of Gryunayzen constant γ shows up in the nonharmonic phenomena. The nonharmonic effects are studied on measuring of elastic characteristics descriptions of crystals.

For measuring of elastic module E and internal friction (IF) the impulse method on frequency $f \approx 1,67; 5$ MHz. A measuring error change of the elastic module $\Delta E/E_0 \approx 0,5\%$ [1,2].

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

The dynamical elastic module $E' = \rho V^2$ and loss module $E'' = E' \delta$:

$$\frac{E''}{E'} = \delta = \pi Q^{-1} = \alpha \lambda = \alpha \frac{V}{f}, \quad (1)$$

where α – ultrasonic (US) attenuation coefficient, λ – the US wave length, f – US frequency. The US attenuation logarithmic decrement δ vibrations with amplitude $A = A_0 e^{-\delta x}$ is equal:

$$\delta = \ln \left(\frac{A_{n+1}}{A_n} \right). \quad (2)$$

The Poisson coefficient μ is equal to ratio of relative transversal compression $\varepsilon_{\perp}$ to relative longitudinal lengthening $\varepsilon_{\parallel}$ and equal [1]:

$$\mu = \frac{\varepsilon_{\perp}}{\varepsilon_{\parallel}} = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \frac{1}{1 - \left(\frac{V}{V_{\perp}} \right)^2} \right]. \quad (3)$$

Debye temperature θ_D was determined after the formula [1]:

$$\theta_D = \frac{h}{k_B} \left(\frac{9\rho N_A}{4\pi A} \right)^{1/3} \left(\frac{1}{V^3} + \frac{2}{V_{\perp}^3} \right)^{1/3}, \quad (4)$$

where k_B - Bol'zman constant, h - Plank constant, N_A - Avogadro number, A - middle gram-molecular mass, ρ - density, $V_{\parallel}$ - longitudinal US velocity, $V_{\perp}$ - transversal US velocity.

The concentration dependences of shear module $G(C)$, elastic module $E(C)$ of nanocomposite low-density polyethylene $(C_2H_4)_n$ + methylene dark blue colouring agent (CH_2) DBSQ at initial state and after electron irradiation with dose $D_e \approx 10$ Mrad and energy $E_e \approx 2,0$ Mev are represented in Figure 1.

Fig. 1 - The concentration dependence of shear module $G(C)$ of nanocomposite low-density polyethylene $(C_2H_4)_n$ + methylene dark blue colouring agent (CH_2) DBSQ at initial state (1) and after electron irradiation with dose $D_e \approx 10$ Mrad and energy $E_e \approx 2,0$ Mev (2)

The depth of the broken layer $h = 1000 \div 3000$ nm is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2 - Dependence of internal friction difference ΔQ^{-1} of SiO_2+Si plate from the depth of the broken layer h

CONCLUSIONS

1. The concentration dependence of shear module $G(C)$, elastic module $E(C)$, strength limit at compression $\sigma_{st}(C)$, elastic limit $\sigma_E(C)$ are represented in consequence of the formation of molecules nanoclusters.
2. The measuring of internal friction background Q^{-1}_0 after different heat, mechanical, radiation treatments gives information about the changing of the thermoelastic strains fields σ_i in SiO_2+Si plates.

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